

USAF Academy Fast-Tracking Telescope

Geoff Andersen, Derek Buzasi, Francis Chun and James Dorman
United States Air Force Academy
HQ USAFA/DFP, Ste 2A31, 2354 Fairchild Dr.,
USAF Academy, CO 80840
719-333-2829
geoff.andersen@usafa.edu

Abstract—We are currently building a new 2m optical observatory at the United States Air Force Academy. Our aim is to create a ground based facility capable of tracking and imaging low Earth and astronomical objects. In conjunction with the Laser and Optics Research Center at the Academy, we can leverage lasers with an extensive range of wavelengths, powers and temporal profiles. This will make it possible to conduct a wide range of experiments involving optical ranging, communications and characterization of satellites. Plans are also being considered to use the telescope to improve the capabilities of a pre-existing thermometric lidar as well as developing innovative lidars for atmospheric analysis and relativistic studies. Future telescope research will also incorporate adaptive optics technologies being developed in the Department of Physics. The telescope will also greatly enhance the astronomical studies of cadets and faculty¹².

The AF Academy took delivery of the \$50 million mirror in 2005 with a view to constructing a ground-based telescope with fast-tracking capabilities. The telescope will be suitable for astronomical (sidereal) operation as well as being capable of tracking low-Earth objects down to altitudes of 200km.

Fig. 1: An image of the 4m LAMP mirror. The circular patterns are diffraction gratings used for phasing the seven segments.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION.....	1
2. TELESCOPE MIRROR	1
3. TELESCOPE DESIGN.....	2
4. RESEARCH	3
5. CONCLUSION	5
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	5
REFERENCES	5
BIOGRAPHY	5

1. INTRODUCTION

The Department of Physics at the United States Air Force Academy is building a 2m telescope for use in Space Situational Awareness projects. The telescope was originally conceived with the endowment of a 4m optical mirror from Air Force Space Command. The segmented primary formed the basis of the Large Aperture Mirror Project (LAMP) for the Space Based Laser development. This project was aimed at testing many technologies associated with creating a large focusing element in space such as active phasing and shaping of a thin mirror (see Fig. 1).

2. TELESCOPE MIRROR

There are two options for the construction of the telescope. One will involve using the hexagonal LAMP mirror provided as Government Furnished Equipment (GFE) segment, while the other will require the contractor supplying a larger mirror of their own.

The GFE mirror:

The mirror cell (government furnished equipment) consists of a glass mirror attached to a graphite composite reaction structure via 66 fine figure screw-motion actuators. The actuators and graphite structure can be either retained or discarded as necessary to meet the construction requirement. The mirror is a hexagonal segment of Ultra-Low Expansion (ULE) glass with a flat-to-flat diameter of 1.6m as shown in Fig. 2. The mass of the 17mm thick glass is estimated to be around 77kg. Since the LAMP telescope was originally designed to function in a Mersenne configuration, the primary figure is parabolic – a conic not particularly suited for two-mirror telescopes.

¹ U.S. Government work not protected by U.S. copyright.

² IEEEAC paper #1238, Version 3, Updated 2008:10:22.

3. TELESCOPE DESIGN

Optical design

The telescope will have a convex secondary and have the following overall performance specifications:

Minimum field of view	5 arcmin (diff. limited) 7 arcmin (0.2" spot size) 20 arcmin (2" seeing)
Operating wavelengths	0.4-2.0 μm
Minimum plate scale	5 arcsec/mm
Total wavefront error	200nm r.m.s.

The design and construction options for the telescope are largely up to the discretion of the contractor so long as the above performance specifications are met. This covers many aspects from the thermalizing of telescope optics to the telescope dimensions and mechanical control. For example, the telescope primary can be constructed from a zero expansion glass or borosilicate glass that is actively cooled. The sole requirement is that the wavefront error budget is met and that the telescope focal plane is always fixed under a range of operating temperatures.

Truss and layout

The telescope will be constructed for instrument operation on one of two Nasmyth platforms. We anticipate that one of these platforms will incorporate optics for correction of field rotation while the other will be uncorrected. The uncorrected output will be used for lidar, single object spectroscopy, photometry and polarimetry. Meanwhile the other focus will be derotated for wide-field/multiobject science and future adaptive optics. The platforms will support two $4^{\circ} \times 6^{\circ}$ damped optical benches for mounting instruments, lasers and optics.

Mounting and tracking

The telescope will be mounted in an altitude-azimuth (alt-az) configuration and will be required to track objects in orbits as low as 200km. The mount (shown schematically in Fig. 3) is currently being designed with the following characteristics:

Azimuth range	$\pm 240^{\circ}$
Altitude range	-2° to keyhole edge
Keyhole	10° (fast-track) 1° (sidereal)
Blind pointing error	5 arcsec (0-70 $^{\circ}$ altitude)
Minimum slew rate	10 degrees/sec
Fast-tracking rate	5 degrees/sec
Fast-tracking error	0.3 arcsec r.m.s.
Sidereal tracking error	0.1 arcsec r.m.s.
Jitter (0.1Hz and 10Hz)	2 arcsec r.m.s.

The requirement of pointing below the horizon is particularly notable. With our unique location we will be

Fig. 2: An image of the central segment of the LAMP mirror (top). The mirror dimensions and hole size are also shown (below).

As a ground-based telescope the FFAs can provide a minor amount of correction for gross gravitational sag. However, since the glass primary is too thin to provide enough internal stiffness to prevent bending under gravity, some inter-actuator deformation is expected. A finite element analysis of this bending for the mirror indicates that we can expect a root mean squared error of $0.23\mu\text{m}$, or 0.3 arcsec seeing. While the ripple will not be a problem initially since site seeing conditions are significantly worse (typically 2-3 arcsec), we hope to remove this error using high-order adaptive optics in the future.

Contractor supplied mirror

It is understood that incorporating unknown technology and materials into a ground based system entails a great deal of risk for potential contractors. For this reason we have agreed to allow the contractor to supply a mirror separate to the GFE primary. If this option is exercised, then the minimum diameter of the contractor mirror is to be 2m. In this case, the primary optical properties and construction can be determined by the contractor subject to meeting the overall telescope performance specifications.

able to use this for ground-to-ground experiments involving transmission of laser beams across large (20-30km) columns of highly turbulent air.

Fig. 3: A schematic of the new telescope with its alt-az mount and Nasmyth platforms.

Location and facilities

The telescope will be located on campus at the US Air Force Academy in Colorado Springs, Colorado (39°00'24" N, 104°52'30 W) at an altitude of 2175m (7130ft). The Academy already has a small observatory (Fig. 4) with computer controlled 0.4m and 0.6m telescopes. For this telescope a new dome will be constructed along with extensions to existing observatory facilities. The telescope location was chosen primarily for accessibility to the cadets.

Fig. 4: The current USAF Academy observatory. The large dome encloses the 0.6m telescope.

On average the site can expect 280 days of cloud-free sky, low humidity and a mean nighttime temperature between -6 and 12°C. The observatory is located only 20km from Colorado Springs itself (population 500,000) and is thus subject to a large amount of light and aerosol pollution. The site is also on the leeward side of the Rocky Mountains which tends to produce moderate to high winds (~5-10 knots average) and poor seeing (2-3 arcsec).

The Academy has 2 other optical telescopes; a 61cm Cassegrain and 41cm Schmidt-Cassegrain, both equatorially mounted. The new telescope will be located in a newly constructed observatory close to the existing building. Concurrent with telescope construction we are planning to make upgrades to our current observatory facilities. These upgrades include refurbishment of the control room and new classroom. Added to this will be new office and laboratory space for development and maintenance of telescope systems and instrumentation.

Instrumentation

Initially we plan to purchase a camera and spectroscope for the telescope, with a view to installing other instruments as necessary. Our back-illuminated camera will have the following properties:

Minimum array size	4096×4096 pixels
Minimum well depth	80,000 e ⁻
Maximum dark current	0.1 e ⁻ /pixel/sec
Quantum efficiency	>90%
Approximate pixel size	15 μm
Minimum readout speed	1 MHz
Maximum readout noise	10 e ⁻

The visible echelle spectrograph will have the following properties:

Spectral coverage	0.3-1.0 μm
Minimum R	20,000
CCD size	2048×2048
Limiting magnitude	12 (10 min integration)

Current status and schedule

It is anticipated that the award date will be in the beginning of 2008 with first light planned for the beginning of 2010.

4. RESEARCH

A 2m-class telescope would be an invaluable tool for many cadet and faculty research projects at the Academy as well as supporting other Air Force operations. The facility will be used for a number of projects in Space Situational Awareness (SSA) and basic research. In each of the project areas detailed below, cadet involvement would be highly encouraged and we anticipate outside collaborations and time available for other users.

Astronomy and astrophysics

The Academy already has a modest astronomical research effort [1-4] which would greatly benefit from a larger telescope. Current research projects include measuring light curves of supernovae, asteroids and stars as well as asteroseismology (high-resolution, time-resolved spectroscopy of bright sources). We are planning to make the telescope available for a larger range of astronomical research topics including planet detection, near Earth asteroid detection and characterization, galactic

characterization and surveys. Since the Academy suffers from poor seeing and significant light and aerosol pollution, the telescope is not expected to be used for deep sky astronomy.

Lidar

The Academy has developed a narrowband holographic spectrophotometer which has been incorporated into a thermometric Raman-Rayleigh lidar [5, 6]. The 25X increase in collecting area of this telescope will greatly improve resolution performance and provide rapid, absolute temperature profiles from ground to space: data critical for the Air Force in many areas ranging from weather forecasting to turbulence avoidance systems. Furthermore, we are currently in the process of improving our lidar with the purchase of a higher power laser.

Fig. 5: A graph of the power and wavelength of selected lasers in the LORC. The top graph shows continuous wave laser while the bottom graph shows the pulsed lasers.

The lidar experiment was developed under support from the Laser and Optics Research Center (LORC) – a research entity attached to the Department of Physics. The LORC has over 10,000 square feet of lab space devoted to a number of projects such as space telescope design, atom trapping, fiber lasers and high power lasers. The LORC is uniquely capable of supporting a wide range of experiments involving laser projection due to the availability of different lasers. The spectral coverage of some of the lasers is shown in Fig. 5 in both continuous wave and pulsed regimes.

Tracking/ranging/surveillance

With the fast-tracking mount, a 2m lidar system could be modified for ranging off satellites [7, 8]. Data collected from these experiments would help us understand the complex relationship between solar activity and atmospheric drag on low-Earth satellites which in turn improves the tracking of objects in orbit. As well as ranging, we will conduct experiments in satellite illumination, optical communications, photometry, polarimetry and imagery.

The Departments of Astronautical Engineering and Physics have for several years led a successful joint effort called FalconSat. This project involves having cadets design, construct, launch and operate microsattellites. The effort usually spans four years and around 140 cadets over this period. A schematic of FalconSat 3 is shown in Fig. 6.

It is anticipated that future missions will utilize the new telescope for experiments relevant to real world SSA issues. For example the simplest experiment would involve installing a number of corner cubes over the satellite for optical ranging studies. A more advanced version of this experiment would involve using modulated corner cubes for optical communications studies. We also anticipate other project involving spacecraft charging by ground-based laser beams and active imaging studies.

Fig. 6: An image of FalconSat 3.

Telescope system test-bed

The LORC is currently developing novel high-power gas lasers [9], ultra-fast wavefront sensors [10] and MEMS-based deformable mirrors [11] which could all be used in next-generation, laser guide star adaptive optics. A telescope of this size is ideally suited for operational testing each of these systems and will ultimately be incorporated into the telescope for superior astronomical imaging and beam projection.

We anticipate using the Fast-Tracking Telescope as a test-bed for instrumentation for other research entities. Often it is difficult to fully check-out instruments that have been constructed for larger telescope facilities. Time on such telescopes is a premium and it can be a challenge to schedule enough time for debugging new devices. We see a good opportunity to make our telescope available for this type of work. With cadet involvement, this can be very instructive in state-of-the-art instrumentation and research techniques.

Holographic correction

The Academy has conducted many experiments [12, 13] involving the holographic correction of aberrated telescopes for various applications. We are currently investigating the possibility of extending our research to a 2m test using the telescope as either the corrected unit or as collimating source for similarly sized membrane mirror.

Teaching

As well as the obvious teaching and research opportunities for the cadets, this instrument gives the Academy the capability to leverage our expertise for the instruction of personnel from other organizations in the fields of low-Earth tracking imaging, communications and ranging.

5. CONCLUSION

The Academy is constructing a 2m-class telescope for operation as a Space Situational Awareness research and teaching facility. First light for the fast-tracking, ground-based telescope will be in 2010. With the aid of lasers already used in research at the Academy, many different projects are planned for this instrument.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to acknowledge support for this project from the Air Force Office of Scientific Research (AFOSR).

REFERENCES

1. J. Cuyper, D. Buzasi, et al, "WIRE Observations of the β Cepheid star β Cru," *Astron. Astrophys.* **392**, 599 (2002).
2. A. Retter, T. R. Bedding, D. L. Buzasi & H. Kjeldsen, "Evidence for Solar-Like Oscillations in Arcturus (α Boo) from WIRE Photometry," *ApJ* **591**:L151-L154 (2002).
3. G. Andersen, "The Telescope: It's History, Technology and Future," Princeton University Press, 2007.
4. C. J. Wetterer and S. Majcen, "CCD Photometry of the Variable Stars V882 Her, V386 Vul and LX Peg," *Inf. Bull. Var. Stars* **5515** (2004).

5. G. Andersen, J. K. Brasseur, R. J. Knize and P. Haris, "Raman and Rayleigh holographic lidar," *Appl. Opt.* **41**, 1798-1804 (2002).
6. For the website of the International Laser Ranging Service: <http://ilrs.gsfc.nasa.gov/>
7. D. Voelz et al, "US/Russian micro-satellite for calibration of active ground-based optical collectors," *Proc. SPIE* **4091**, 278-282 (2000).
8. D. M. Boroson, A. Biswas and B. L. Edwards, "MLCD: Overview of NASA's Mars Laser Communications Demonstration System," *Proc SPIE* **5338** (2004).
9. B.V. Zhdanov and R.J. Knize, "Diode Pumped 10 Watts Continuous Wave Cesium Laser," *Optics Letters* **32**, 2167-2169, (2007).
10. G. Andersen, F. Ghebremichael and K. Gurley, "Holographic Wavefront Sensor – Fast Sensing, No Computing", "Practical Holography XXI: Materials and Applications", *Proc. SPIE* **6488**, 64880I, (2007).
11. M. A. Michalick, J. H. Comtois and H. K. Schriener, "Geometry versus optical performance of micromirrors and arrays," *Proc. SPIE* **3440**, 140-147 (1998).
12. G. Andersen and R. J. Knize, "Holographically corrected telescope for high bandwidth optical communications," *Appl. Opt.* **38**, 6833-6835 (1999).
13. G. Andersen and R. J. Knize, "Large-aperture holographically corrected membrane telescope," *Opt. Eng.* **41**, 1603-1607 (2002).

BIOGRAPHY

Dr. Geoff Andersen earned his Ph.D. in physics from the University of Adelaide, Australia. Since 1996 he has been employed as a research associate with the Laser and Optics Research Center, part of the Department of Physics at the US Air Force Academy. His

research specialties include holography, telescope design and lidar. He has authored 14 journal papers, 30 conference proceedings and a book entitled "The telescope: its history, technology and future".

Dr. Francis Chun received a B.S. degree in Space Physics from the United States Air Force Academy in 1983, and a Ph.D. in Geophysics and Space Physics from the University of California, Los Angeles, in 1992. He has spent over 20 years on active duty for the Air Force before retiring in 2003. He has published 11 articles in peer-

review space physics journals and has over 40 conference presentations. Dr. Chun was awarded the 1999 Frank J. Seiler Award for Research Excellence at the Air Force Academy. Currently, he is Project Manager for the USAF Academy Fast-Tracking Telescope program.

James Dorman spent over 26 years on active duty in the United States Air Force with various operational assignments including an aircraft navigator and combat planner, Assistant Professor of physics at the USAF Academy, and as lead in nuclear non-proliferation/treaty compliance organizations. Since

his retirement from active duty in 2004, he has served as project manager/project administrator for three major research initiatives at the Department of Physics at the USAF Academy.

Dr. Derek Buzasi received a B.Sc. in physics from the University of Chicago in 1985 and a Ph. D. in astronomy from Penn State in 1989. He has worked for NCAR, Johns Hopkins University, NASA and UC Berkeley before coming to the USAF Academy. Since 2000 he has been a Professor in the Department of Physics

specializing in stellar atmospheres and astronomy. Dr. Buzasi is also a Lt. Commander in the US Navy and recently accepted a position as PSNS SURGMAIN program manager at Puget Sound Naval Base.